

The ecology of surface

Within and beyond communities in transformation through macro-paintings

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Introduction

In recent years, macro-paintings have become a popular tool through which various actors try to uplift communities in cities of the global South by painting their material environment.¹ A macro-painting is essentially a massive painting that covers dozens, sometimes even hundreds, of houses in marginal neighborhoods. These actors operate under the assumption that improving the material conditions of these communities will lead to their overall transformation. While communities represent a key unit in this process on which macro-paintings are intended to impact, macro-paintings, *de facto*, create new spaces and boundaries in each territory and city.

In this brief paper, we want to shed light on the phenomenon of macro-painting by thinking of them within and beyond the community. In doing so, we are concerned with “exploring ephemeral processes of presencing and proximity, accounting for the intermingling of interiority and exteriority” (Robinson 2013, 8). Based on interviews with various actors from different countries of Latin America, we analyse the boundaries of diverse scales of macro-paintings – houses, neighbourhoods/districts, cities – and argue that macro-paintings produce their unique ecology through which they affect meanings, materialities and lives all over the city. We believe public art always represents the history and vital events of given sites and the country. It becomes a testimony of the context in which they were created, thus entering repeatedly as an actor into the present day. So, democracy, citizenship, or identity are all linked in some way with graffiti, street art, and (macro)murals in Latin American cities (Dabène 2020).

To understand these nuances – of materialities, imaginaries, and practices – we think of our materials through the concept of *surface* (Philippopoulos-Mihalopoulos and Brighenti Eds. 2018). We claim that the concept very well captures potential links between a painting and the city and, at the same time, provokes us to rethink the crucial issues that this connection brings into conversation. In this, we follow the articulations of surfaces, “interested in what surfaces can do and how they come about in social life” (Anusas and Simonetti 2021, 10), which holds broader significance for urban studies.

Macro-paintings in Latin America

Around 30% of all the inhabitants of current cities live in so-called *slums*: self-built settlements con-

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structed by inhabitants on illegally occupied land using only locally available materials (UN-HABITAT 2003). Although settlements differ globally in history and shape as much as scale and demography, they are all characterized by being illegal responses to the basic human need for secure housing (Álvarez-Rivadulla 2017), and just the materialization of this need becomes most often a convenient surface for macro-paintings.

On the scale of the community, these settlements represent vulnerable territories exposed to poverty and marginalisation. In this sense, for instance, a recent report on Altos de la Florida, a self-built settlement in Soacha in the south of Bogotá, informed that around 73% of dwellers live in poverty (Internal Displacement Monitoring Center 2020). Usually, houses in these territories are structurally and materially inadequate, creating a visually uneven surface characteristic of self-built settlements. As a result of peripheral urbanization (Caldeira 2017), infrastructures can be dire in these neighborhoods: unpaved roads, lack of sanitation, or missing garbage collection. Given all these attributes, communities face suspicions and stigmatisation from the dwellers in surrounding areas and the rest of the city. By creating a visible surface through the use of colors and patterns, macro-paintings aim to integrate the neighborhoods into the urban fabric.

Since 2010, mobilized by various actors, these paintings have spread as a general concept across Latin America and even beyond. Nowadays, we can find such projects in Mexico, Puerto Rico, Colombia, Bolivia, Peru, Brazil, and Haiti. In all these countries, art collectives and local governments, cooperating with residents, attempt to transform local communities. To understand this trend, we conducted interviews on 18 individual projects across 6 countries, carried out by eight different collectives or artists. Though outcomes are mainly evident in the material intervention of macro-paintings, every unit of scale also reflects different social and political effects.

Macro-paintings represent an ecologically, socio-materially, politically relational, and multi-sited assemblage (Vašát 2024). All the murals discussed here are shaped through the effects of mountains, and through a network of practical but also symbolic relations with other parts of the city, the ability to see the artworks from inside/outside has emerged. Moreover, ecological aspects and environmental conditions – from animals and flowers to rivers to wind – very often become the themes of paintings chosen by residents during workshops organized by urban authorities and their mediators. The projects are then coordinated mainly by the city authorities, delegating responsibilities and tasks, and the participation of other actors is usually affirmed by legal contracts involving not only the artists but also the residents of a given neighbourhood. And if legality is not directly established – sometimes the legal character of a given territory may be disputed – then at least a considerable degree of institutionally practiced formality is usually achieved. They are a specific reminder that in urbanisation of Latin American cities, “materiality and political economy are always already co-continued” (Schindler 2017, 56) and thus much more than the mere (painted) surface of this materiality.

Within and beyond communities undergoing transformation

At the smallest unit of scale, macro-painting produces a novel boundary between individual houses. This can have two general socio-material implications – one materializing as an impact of participation, the other resulting from refusal. Particularly, houses in self-built or popular settlements are usually never finished and represent a project that has been continuously evolving (Houston 1990; Caldeira 2017). Given this fact, residents occasionally do not agree with a project and forbid their houses from being included. Tomás Darío, from Colectivo Tomate, explained how in the process of the macro-painting *Colosal* in Monterrey, Mexico, some neighbors did not want their walls to be touched because they had plans to improve them with plaster in the future. It would, therefore, be futile to paint them: “We do not want to impose; we like to invite people to choose whether they want to participate or not” (2 April 2023, online interview). More generally speaking, in a macro-painting, as

the exterior wall becomes public, it might represent a loss of autonomy over property. A similar effect occurs among residents who decide to participate in a project. The material outcome is co-produced by the (auto)construction phase in which a particular house finds itself. As implied above, the colored surface of bricks slightly complicates insulation as the paving makes it difficult for the plaster to stick to the wall. Through the decisions they impose, the projects instigate material and affective differences between individual houses and their residents.

The new boundary is also being created at the scale of community. Either directly through the city's surfaces or by reproducing pictures on the Internet, macromurals attract the strong attention of tourists and the general public. Some macro-paintings involve smaller graffiti and murals on the walls in between, usually made for tourist tours. Such tours can be found in Bogotá, Colombia, as part of the macro-painting *El Luna Sol* and *La Mariposa*. These tours offer people the chance to experience local food, such as *buñuelos* (fried cheesy pastries) in La Mariposa, or buy products made by local artists, such as bracelets in Buenavista. However, once again, these graffiti and murals, products, and tourist trajectories through the geography of the *barrio* (neighborhood) are associated only with some communities or their parts. Only the chosen ones are visible enough and thus accessible to potential socio-economic benefits that these spatial attributes offer.

Macro-paintings are largely dependent on the topographical nature of the site, conditioning their size and the unique perspectives that enable the visibility of the painting. As such, they have the capacity to transform the narratives of places and create upstart boundaries that differentiate them from, and connect to, the urban surroundings. In Lima, Peru, the macro-painting *El Gran Telar* sought to make visible a neighborhood that is very close to the city center but remained segregated from it. Daniel Manrique, from Color Energía collective in Peru, mentioned how through *El Gran Telar*, the *barrio* Leticia became the one colorful neighborhood amidst the grayness: "Lima is a gray city, but this is no longer a gray neighbourhood." (21 February 2023, online interview). The new, colorful identity produced by the macro-paintings creates an unequivocal sense of pride among many neighbors who see their *barrio* transformed into a livelier place. Additionally, as a material-discursive entity, the painting intervenes in the world of representations and symbols, when challenging prevalent negative depictions associated with the neighborhood. Despite this intervention, while the potential for tourism and the creation of a new identity have been established for one district, the remainder of the city, with its pervasive 'grayness' and accompanying challenges, remains largely unchanged in this regard.

Conclusion: Towards the ecology of surface

This paper explores macro-painting as a manifestation of urban surface. Within this perspective, a territory of macro-painting represents a distinct "textured surface that accelerates and decelerates, where interruptions foster diverse points of view, attentiveness, memories, consolidations, and dispersions of effort and association" (Simon 2011, 356). Macro-paintings transcend being merely specific entities that arise from the interplay of mind, body, and materiality (Ingold 2013); they transform into a form that, by virtue of evolving surfaces, forges intricate relationships with the urban bodies and surfaces. In essence, they are in a state of becoming, characterized by a "continuous interstitial knitting, rather than a fixed strata of matter" (Anusas and Simonetti 2021, 4-5). Consequently, macro-paintings possess the capacity to inscribe themselves in the urban landscape through diverse trajectories and multifaceted means.

Inspired by Isabelle Stengers' writings on the "ecology of practices" (2005, 2018), we argue that these inscriptions can be approached and understood through the ecological framework that a macro-painting's surface creates. From this perspective, ecology represents 'the interrelations between heterogeneous beings as such, without a transcendent common interest' (Stengers 2018, 91). To comprehend specific practices, one must explicitly consider the habitat of these practices because,

as Stengers (2005, 195) reminds us, “a practice is part of the surroundings that produce its ethos.” In this sense, the unique ecology of macro-paintings introduces new spatial practices (e.g., tourist tours) that may limit or alter practices associated with a territory (e.g., insulation). However, this ecology of surface is not a static or permanent spatial condition; it presupposes changes in the rhythms of practices, the speed of processes, or the temporality of outcomes.

Although macro-paintings certainly do not address the full range of problems associated with poverty and inequality, they have significant effects on cities. On the one hand, as we have illustrated here, they create new sources of income and foster a sense of coalescence and belonging within communities. On the other hand, much like burgeoning vernacular architecture (Grubbauer 2017), they may become a new fetish for urban authorities. Similar to philanthropically motivated infrastructure upgrades in slums, they can pose a threat to residents, potentially leading to the loss of their homes (Desai and Loftus 2012). Or, akin to street art in general, they might contribute to the gentrification of adjacent parts of the city where they are visible (Schacter 2014).

Nevertheless, before we embark on an investigation into whether and how the specific relationships with the components through which they are adopted – be it institutional, ecological, socio-material, or socio-spatial (Vašát 2024) – determine their outcomes, we must first understand the results produced as a consequence of a general array of limited but recurring practices. This underscores the importance of recognizing that seemingly invisible and homogenized urban surfaces are not inert (Brighenti and Kärholm Eds. 2018); they have broader spatial consequences that scholars must thoroughly investigate.

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